

HOW DOES THE LEARNER'S AUTONOMY IMPACT ON STUDENTS ACHIEVEMENT IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

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One way to increase motivation for learning autonomy is to provide students with the opportunity to be the subject of the learning process rather than its recipient, despite the danger that some students are not ready to take responsibility for the process and results of their learning. However, learner autonomy in relation to learning should not only be seen as a goal for active students only, but also as a fundamental learning goal for all students [3].

There are two main arguments for learner autonomy. Firstly, if they engage in a foreign language meaningfully, autonomy will be effective and efficient, since it is more personally oriented. Secondly, if students are active and engaged learners, then by definition there is no problem of motivation, although they may not always have a positive attitude towards all aspects of their learning. In the case of a foreign language, there is a third argument. Effective communication depends on a set of practical (methodological) skills that are formed only in the process of communication. Students with a high degree of social autonomy in a learning environment will find it easier to master the full range of roles on which their effective spontaneous communication depends [1].

When revealing the content of the term “student autonomy”, there is an ambiguous interpretation of it, since it is often mistakenly equated with independent educational work (self-instruction). A number of studies on the issue of autonomy discuss the following issues: should learner autonomy be considered as a property of behavior; whether it is characterized by responsibility for managing the educational process; whether autonomy is a psychological phenomenon with political overtones or a political right with psychological overtones; does the development of student autonomy depend on the autonomy of the teacher, etc. [2].

What is meant here is that the political connotation refers to the idea of human freedom of choice in general and, in the context of education, the ability for students to “take control” or make decisions regarding their learning when they are limited in what they can do. In practice, this means that the economic and other difficulties of certain population groups, as well as government educational policies, curricula, and the use of “compulsory” textbooks are examples of ways in which the development of autonomy can be hampered.

Some teachers, however, try to overcome these difficulties, but this happens quite rarely. It is recognized in scientific circles that the autonomous learner must understand the purpose of the training program, take responsibility for his own learning, participate in setting learning goals, must take initiative in planning and executing practical learning tasks, systematically review his learning and evaluate its effectiveness [2]. It is also recognized that the practical implementation of student autonomy requires a positive attitude towards them on the part of teachers, since autonomy is the ability to reflect and the willingness to be proactive in self-government and interaction with others.

The development of autonomy is a long-term process, and its successful implementation in the educational process largely depends on the persistence of the teacher. It is not possible to expect students to be able to take responsibility for their own learning in one day or even a month. Autonomy develops gradually and requires an independent way of thinking, which can be greatly facilitated by the general atmosphere in the classroom, which stimulates students' thinking, encourages them to have different points of view and helps students understand their role in the learning process.

In foreign science, theories of the development of student autonomy are known. Thus, David Nunan, viewing the curriculum in terms of autonomy and a learner-centered approach, proposes “nine steps” in moving students from dependence to autonomy. According to the author, the development of autonomy is facilitated by: 1) learning goals that are understandable to students, which are realized through the active involvement of students in the learning process, while avoiding simple information; 2) providing students with the opportunity to set their own goals and change the content of the course of study; 3) encouraging the use of a foreign language by students outside the classroom; 4) increasing the level of understanding of the educational process; 5) formation of students' own learning styles and strategies; 6) encouraging students to make independent choices in decision-making; 7) providing students with the opportunity to adapt and modify classroom activities according to their preferences; 8) providing students with the opportunity to act as a teacher; 9) providing students with the opportunity to act as a researcher [3].

Subsequently, Hayo Renders develops a theory of autonomy based on the results of previous research. So, first of all, Hayo Renders considers it necessary to determine the needs of students in their learning of a foreign language, to study the weaknesses and strengths of the entire study group and each student individually, to encourage students' desire to share the positive results of their

studies. Regarding goal setting, the author agrees with David Nunan's belief that students who have reached the level where they can set their own goals and create their own learning opportunities have become autonomous [1]. At the same time, attention is drawn to the fact that the teacher cannot ignore the curriculum, so he must encourage the perception of the course of study as one of the elements of students achieving their goals. An important aspect of student autonomy is also the opportunity for them to experiment with language material and go beyond the educational environment, including acquired knowledge in the realities of everyday life. When organizing independent work outside the classroom, you should avoid the same type of training exercises that do not provide feedback. Reflection is important for developing autonomy. Therefore, an effective tool for this process can be a language portfolio, which performs both a controlling function and a self-control function. The language portfolio is an alternative means of assessing the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students. Its use in the learning process gives students confidence in their abilities and stimulates their motivation for further learning. The student's awareness that he is valued as an individual, a sense of support, as well as active involvement in the learning process undoubtedly contributes to the student's development of autonomous thinking and his participation in planning, practical implementation of goals and evaluation of the results of his learning. However, the introduction of a system of gradual transition to autonomy does not guarantee a complete shift in emphasis from the teacher to the student [3].

Interpreting foreign theories of the development of autonomy, it should be noted that for non-linguist students, especially at the initial stage of training, factors such as the creation of favorable external conditions for the realization of their internal aspirations for mastering a foreign language and culture are very important; updating the personal and professional needs of economics students in learning a foreign language and culture; development of meta-cognitive strategies for mastering a foreign language, development of self-learning competence; development of learning tools that allow students at the initial stage of education to achieve a basic level of foreign language proficiency that meets the requirements of the program, and an advanced level for ambitious students who set higher goals for themselves; development of means for self-control, assessment of one's educational activities as a whole and determination of one's level of foreign language proficiency for the purpose of further improvement. Thus, to help a student successfully achieve his goal, it is necessary to increase his level of learning autonomy. Autonomy plays a very

important role in the educational process, since at each level of his education the student plans his own educational trajectory, which guides his activities in achieving his goal, including the student's education at a university of professional interest to him and foreign internships.

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